

DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL LITERACY: A REPORT OF THE POTENTIAL USE OF LESSON STUDY WITHIN ITE

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All students should have access to quality mathematics education. Given the documented impact teachers have on learning outcomes in mathematics, it is essential that initial teacher education develop the relevant knowledge and aptitudes among pre-service teachers to facilitate them to teach mathematics effectively. This paper focuses on the potential role of Lesson Study within initial teacher education in meeting this goal. In particular, we examine the various opportunities and benefits that are available to each of the 'partners' engaging in Lesson Study. Over a decade we have explored the benefits of Lesson Study using a three-tier teaching experiment approach (Lesh & Kelly, 2000). This approach facilitates insights into the effects of participation in Lesson Study from the perspectives of the three partners: teacher educator, the student teacher and the pupils.

LESSON STUDY

Lesson study (LS) originated in Japan and has traditionally been used within schools as a bottom-up school-based form of professional development. Through this process, a cycle of planning, teaching and reflection takes place. Initially, a group of teachers come together to form a lesson study group (LSG). This LSG selects a subject, teaching approach or skill they wish to improve and work together to plan a detailed single lesson called a research lesson. This lesson plan anticipates learners' strategies, misconceptions and responses. One of the LSG members teaches this first lesson (teach 1) and all other members observe the lesson whilst focusing in particular on pupil learning. Through this process of observation, reflection and discussion the LSG revise the initial research lesson and a second LSG member reteaches the revised research lesson to a different class group (teach 2). This cycle of planning, observation, reflection and discussion can be repeated many times over weeks or even months. In some cases, 'knowledgeable others' engage with the LSG to provide support at various stages. LS concludes with the LSG sharing their learning through a written report (Murata, 2011).

The above approach is referred to as 'traditional' or 'formal' LS. In Japan, the majority of teachers engage with formal LS annually. Outside of Japan, the use of LS has spread over time among qualified teachers. Research reports various benefits associated with engaging in formal LS including improved practice with a greater emphasis on student learning, enhanced teacher knowledge, increased teacher commitment and collaboration, and the development of learning resources (Chassels and Melville, 2009; Murata, 2011; Ní Shuilleabhain, 2016). However, implementing LS within schools presents a series of challenges including cost (e.g. substitute teachers), sustainability (engagement for one term/year versus ongoing participation) and issues in supporting effective teaching practices among teachers with limited content knowledge (Murata, 2011).

Lesson Study in Initial Teacher Education

Over time, interest in the potential of LS within initial teacher education (ITE) has increased. However, due to limited time within already crowded ITE courses LS has inevitably taken many forms (Cohan and Honigsfeld, 2007). Adaptations include ‘Microteaching LS’, where pre-service teachers (PSTs) teach research lessons to their peers (Fernandez, 2005). Other modifications include compressed LS cycles (1 day) (McMahon and Hines, 2008) or Lesson Plan Study where PSTs engage in the collaborative planning phase only (no implementation) (Cavey and Berenson, 2005). Other variants situate the planning phase in the university setting, involve research lessons being taught and videoed during school practicum and subsequently evaluated on return to university (Cohan and Honigsfeld, 2007). Despite these restrictions placed on adapted models of LS, studies report positive outcomes for PSTs including improved content knowledge (Cavey and Berenson, 2005), the development of collaborative and reflective practice as well as a move towards more learner-centred pedagogy (Fernandez, 2005).

A relatively small number of studies use a more traditional LS structure (Leavy and Hourigan, 2016; Marble, 2006; Chassels and Melville, 2009; Sims and Walsh, 2009; Corcoran and Pepperell, 2011; Cajkler et al., 2013; Cajkler and Wood, 2016a; 2016b; 2018). However, the majority of these LSs were implemented as part of the school practicum component of ITE with the co-operation of mentor teachers (Chassels and Melville, 2009; Cajkler and Wood, 2016a; 2016b; 2018). Reported challenges associated with implementing LS within ITE programmes include scheduling problems, limited time for collaboration and debriefing, the inability to access a suitable class for the reteach, difficulties securing suitable qualified mentors (Chassels and Melville, 2009; Cajkler and Wood, 2016b) and insufficient knowledge of classroom students (Chassels and Melville, 2009). Despite these issues, the reported benefits of implementing formal LS in ITE generally reflect those reported for qualified teachers (Chassels and Melville, 2009; Bjuland and Mosvold, 2015; Cajkler and Wood, 2018; Leavy, 2010, 2015; Leavy and Hourigan, 2016, 2018a).

This paper examines the various outcomes of a particular model of formal LS within an ITE programme. This model differs from the majority of others in ITE, as the LS was not based around or within the PSTs’ school practicum. Instead, the implementation of the research lessons was facilitated by co-ordinating with local partner schools.

METHODOLOGY

To support the observation and analysis of outcomes arising from engaging in LS in ITE, annually a three-tier perspective (Lesh and Kelly, 2000) was taken. Tier 1 focuses on the impact of LS on primary school children (for example the nature of their developing mathematical knowledge and abilities). Tier 2 focuses on the impact of LS participation on PSTs (for example their developing knowledge, assumptions about the nature of students’ mathematical knowledge and abilities). Tier 3 concentrates on researcher (teacher educators) characteristics (for example their evolving teacher educator identity or their developing conceptions about the nature of children’s and pre-service teachers’ developing knowledge

and abilities). The design involves the ongoing collection of data at each stage of the LS cycle from multiple sources.

Participants

Annually (2008-2017) the researchers worked with a small group of undergraduate primary PSTs (maximum of 25) who had opted to participate in an elective mathematics education course during the 3rd year of their 4-year ITE course in Ireland. These PSTs had completed all 5 compulsory mathematics education modules which addressed the content and pedagogy related to the range of curriculum strands. In terms of school placement, prior to the study PSTs had engaged in at least 10 weeks of placement in a range of classes. LS research lessons were taught predominantly within 2 local schools with whom we have an informal partnership. All ethical requirements were completed including institutional ethical approval, school Board of Management permission, and information and consent provided in the form of information letters and consent forms for all the relevant participants.

The nature of formal Lesson Study within this study

Within this study, participating PSTs experienced a formal LS approach within their ITE programme.

Stage 1: At the start of the module (Stage 1 of the LS cycle; Table 1), PSTs were introduced to the process of LS as implemented in Japan. They engaged with various key LS readings such as Stigler and Hiebert (1999) and considered the strengths and weaknesses of this model and its applicability to the Irish context.

Stage 2: Subsequently, the PSTs moved into the planning stage (approximately 6 weeks) of the LS cycle (Stage 2; Table 1). In order to facilitate ongoing co-operation from volunteering schools and teachers, each year a sequence of 5 research lessons (developed by 5 lesson study groups) over 5 consecutive days replaced the class teacher's mathematics lessons for a teaching week. While the researchers (in their role of teacher educators) decided the mathematical area (e.g. strand of Algebra) and/or mathematical concepts (e.g. Equality, Functions, Variables) which would be addressed, the PSTs had a central role in deciding the teaching sequence, methodologies, contexts, materials and in related pedagogical and content decision making. To inform their decisions, PSTs were assigned relevant readings (e.g. academic and practitioner articles) and various international curricula. This process led to discussions regarding the assignment of concepts to specific research lessons and subsequently appropriate contexts that could motivate children to engage. PSTs were assigned to a LSG; with each LSG responsible for planning and teaching a designated lesson. We use the lesson plan format devised by Ertle, Chokshi and Fernandez's (2001) as it required PSTs to explicitly attend to expected student responses and the teacher's response to student activity/response. The researchers (in their role as knowledgeable others) met each LSG weekly both during and outside of lecture time to work on the planning of the research lesson. Subsequently, each LSG implemented their research lesson (in sequence) to a designated class level in school 1 across 5 consecutive days. While one PST taught the first lesson (teach 1), the remaining LSG members assumed the role of observers. Immediately after lesson implementation, the researchers and the LSG met to share and discuss observations and

determine the necessary revisions to the research lesson. Teach 2, which took place two weeks later in school 2 to a different group of children at the same grade level, was video-recorded by a professional video crew. Again, the process of observation, discussion and reflection resulted in further refining of the research lesson. Class teachers (in both settings) provided informal feedback based on observations.

Stage 3: The final stage, which lasted two weeks (Stage 3; Table 1), focused on reflection and reporting on the LS process. Each LSG made a presentation describing and critiquing their research lesson. PSTs also completed reflective assignments at the end of semester focusing on areas such as the development of children’s understandings of the relevant concepts, perceptions of their own learning and experience of the LS process.

Table 1. Structure and focus of each LS cycle stage and related data collection methods

LS Stages		Primary Activities	Data Collection Methods
Stage 1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduce LS • Explore and discuss key readings relating to LS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher field notes taken during tutorials and work sessions • Researcher reflective journal entries
Stage 2	Step 1: Collaborative planning of the research lesson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the relevant mathematics concepts • Develop a trajectory of instruction • Identify the key foci for each LSG • Design the research lessons 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher field notes taken during tutorials and work sessions • Researcher reflective journal entries • Content analysis of lesson
	Step 2: ‘First teach’: Seeing the research lesson in action	Each of the LSGs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teach the lesson • Observe the lesson and make notes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observations of first lesson implementation • Researcher reflective journal entries
	Step 3: Reflection, discussion and revision	Each of the LSGs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the taught lesson • Revise the original research lesson 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher field notes taken during feedback session • Participant reflections • Record of changes made to revised lesson and justification of those changes • Researcher reflective journal entries
	Step 4: ‘Second teach’: Seeing the research lesson in action	Each of the LSGs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teach the revised lesson • Observe the lesson and make notes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observations of second lesson implementation • Video records of second lesson • Researcher reflective journal entries
	Step 5: Reflection, discussion and revision	Each of the LSGs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reflect on the taught lesson • Make final revisions to the research lesson 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher field notes taken during feedback session • Record of changes made to revised lesson and justification of those changes • Researcher reflective journal entries
Stage 3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LSG presentations • Individual pre-service teacher reflections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Records and observations of LSG presentations • Participant reflections • Researcher reflective journal entries

Data collection and analysis

A mixed-method approach was taken to data collection. Table 1 summarises the nature, source and range of data collected at each stage of the LS cycle. These included field notes and recorded conversations from all stages (planning meetings, post-teach meetings), lesson plans, samples of children's work, researcher observations, videos of teach 2, PST and researcher reflections and group presentations. While acknowledging the limitations of self-report data, the variety of data sources serve to strengthen the findings. The issues of reliability and validity are particularly important when utilising qualitative methodologies as much of the data is in the form of communicated opinions, attitudes and beliefs which may well contain a certain degree of bias. A number of measures were taken to combat bias and ensure verisimilitude. Firstly, the researchers collected data from a number of perspectives and sources throughout the various LS stages (See Table 1). Transcripts reflected verbatim accounts of both researchers', PSTs' and children's ideas, opinions and understandings (McMillan and Schumacher, 2001). Secondly, a systematic process of data analysis was undertaken where the raw data were initially organised into natural units using representative codes (Creswell, 2009). Successive examinations of the data led to the identification of relationships between codes and subsequently the creation of overarching themes. Thus, across all studies, data were analysed using a grounded theory approach, where the data steered the emerging theory.

SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS AND OUTPUTS FROM LS

Over the decade, while the approach to formal Lesson Study has been consistent, our research focus has varied. Our research interests shift in response to local and national areas of priority and interest. Some examples of research foci include our own evolving identity as teacher educators, PSTs' perceptions of what they had learned, PSTs' content knowledge and children's evolving understandings as a result of engaging in research lessons. The three tier model alongside the range of potential foci within each tier illustrates the usefulness, fluidity and productivity of Lesson Study as a process for all participants (teacher educators, PSTs and learners).

Focusing on Tier 1, annually we are interested in examining the growth of children's understandings of various mathematical concepts as a result of engaging in the research lessons arising from the LS. For example, we have examined the nature of young children's understandings of various statistical concepts including their use of inscriptions in statistical investigations (Leavy and Hourigan, 2018b) as well as the selection of attributes in data modelling environments (Leavy and Hourigan, 2018c). At Tier 2, our research has examined the impact of engaging in LS on PSTs mathematical knowledge for teaching. This model of Lesson Study has been found to have a positive impact on developing both mathematics content knowledge as well as pedagogical content knowledge (Leavy, 2010, 2015; Leavy and Hourigan, 2016, 2018a; O' Ceallaigh, Hourigan and Leavy, 2019). Throughout, the researchers are constantly reflecting and learning themselves (Tier 3) about the mathematical and pedagogical considerations of the mathematical concepts under study any one year. When deciding to engage in LS within an Irish immersion setting, while the authors were considered 'old timers' in the world of LS, they were 'newcomers' to the world of immersion teacher

education. As part of this process, we examined the nature of our evolving immersion teacher educator identity over the course of this project (Leavy, Hourigan and O’Ceallaigh, 2018).

We acknowledge that, in its present form, LS has limited impact with only a small proportion of PSTs annually having the opportunity to engage with LS. However, we believe that Lesson Study can potentially have a more widespread and positive impact on the PSTs and qualified teachers beyond those directly involved. One way this is possible is through the sharing of research lessons created within the LS process in relevant national and international practitioner journals (see this link as an example of how we endeavour to make our outputs freely accessible to educators <https://www.mic.ul.ie/faculty-of-education/department/stem-education?index=5>). These dissemination efforts provide both practicing and prospective primary teachers with relatable experiences; providing examples of reform-oriented teaching contexts, learner-centred activities, varied pedagogies. These articles also explore children’s thinking and evolving conceptions. Such resources have the potential to provide support for teachers and enhance their mathematics knowledge for teaching.

Another valuable means of increasing the impact of LS is through the digital recording of the research lessons, particularly those revised lessons taught in the second cycle of LS. These video case studies can be used within ITE mathematics education sessions to give the general population of PSTs access to the concepts, contexts, pedagogies and children’s thinking for the various areas of the mathematics curriculum. Rather than use dated video footage, or footage of qualified teachers, or classes from another context, our experiences is that PSTs relate better to footage of Irish PSTs teaching in Irish primary schools.

This paper highlights that Lesson Study can potentially contribute to all of the partners’ understandings of various pertinent aspects of effective mathematics education.

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